

Social, technical and political transformations in OpenStreetMap – From volunteered geographic information to embedding digital commons in platform capitalism

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This abstract was accepted to the OSM Science 2023 Conference after peer-review.

Since its early days OpenStreetMap (OSM) has developed from a small mapping project carried out mainly by mapping enthusiasts with a vision to create an open map of the world to a project that actually can compare its coverage to proprietary providers of mapping data, including Google [1]. Against the background of a world that increasingly relies on geospatial data, the role of OSM is changing in multiple ways. This study focuses from a social and digital geography perspective on the changing social, technical and political conditions underlying OSM and aims to argue how OSM, along with the geospatial industry as a whole, is approaching a stage of maturity, yet remains true to itself at its core. The larger research question behind this paper is how the OSM project is addressing the ever-increasing economic and geopolitical tensions in which it finds itself.

The empirical results of this study focus mainly on developments of OSM over the last four years. Quantitative analysis of OSM data (OSM full history dump and changeset dumps) and qualitative analysis of other online sources (OSM wikis, blogs, forums) were used to explore the growing interest or role of institutional actors in OSM. To gain a deeper understanding of the OSM ecosystem, this research involved attending conferences both online and in the field, and conducting around 30 expert interviews with members of the OSM community, as well as with individuals in the geospatial data industry. These interviews, which were analyzed using methods of qualitative content analysis, gave intriguing insights into the geospatial industry and the embedding of open mapping projects like OSM into it.

The results of this study are categorized into 1) social, 2) technical, and 3) political transformations in OSM, which are conceptualized in a larger context.

1) In recent years, there has been social shifts in the participating groups of OSM, as well as the spatial distribution of contributors. In total OSM became a much more diverse and global project. Not least, organized editing groups – humanitarian mapping teams like

Schröder-Bergen, S. (2023). Social, technical and political transformations in OpenStreetMap – From volunteered geographic information to embedding digital commons in platform capitalism

In: Minghini, M., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., Liu, P., Yeboah, G., Juhász, L., Coetzee, S., Mooney, P., Sarretta, A., & Anderson, J. (Eds.). Proceedings of the OSM Science at State of the Map Europe 2023, Antwerp, Belgium, 10-12 November 2023. Available at

<https://zenodo.org/communities/osmscience-2023>

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10443321](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10443321)

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HOT and commercial actors – have made the project more known in parts of the world that have not been the main core of OSM. It can be argued that this development has both an empowering effect for new participants from formerly underrepresented regions and might be suppressing local voices when external worldviews are reproduced [2].

2) This is also reflected in technical shifts within OSM. With the greater engagement of organized mapping groups in OSM, a distinction between local knowledge versus remote data makes less sense. The attention has instead changed towards the difference between volunteered and paid or corporate mapping [3]. These new more institutionalized mapping groups also introduce new “modes” of mapping into the OSM ecosystem, including, for example, dealing with machine learning generated datasets [4].

3) Tentatively and only partly, there are, within the OSM community, also trends towards a greater discussion and recognition of the potential social (and political) responsibility that OSM entails as a large, global project [5,6]. This comes also in light of the recent creation of the Overture Maps Foundation. The increasing significance of (open) geospatial data for a multitude of actors – both private and public – positions the project, which has always seen itself as apolitical and global, in a political arena that goes far beyond concrete data conflict issues, such as where to draw a boundary line in a crisis region, to the handling and protection of the OSM project, the data, and the community as a whole. Recent developments and the handling within OSM, however, suggest that the way OSM works may also be the reason that OSM is so resistant and independent to other interested parties (of the broader geospatial industry) who would like to steer the project in their desired direction.

These transformations are symptomatic of larger trends in OSM, which can be conceptualized as an evolution of OSM from a volunteered geographic information (VGI) project to OSM as a project embedded in platform capitalist logics [7]. In addition, the success of OSM can be seen as particularly rooted in internal socio-technical elements of OSM that follow the principles of digital commoning. The concept of digital commons focuses on alternatives to capitalist political economies that remain within market-structured environments, but that emphasizes the openness and resistance of digital domains that are structured through specific practices of regulation [8,9]. It seems analytically useful to frame the socio-technical practices of data production and use in OSM with its specific formal and informal regulations as a form of digital commoning.

This paper situates the current state of OSM in the larger context of a world that is increasingly reliant on geospatial data. OSM is becoming more and more global and also increasingly important for the entire geospatial domain. This means that it is also becoming interesting for highly resourced and powerful actors. OSM must consequently deal more and more with the economic and geopolitical areas of tension of the digital transformation. Questions arise whether the existing structures and rules within OSM are sufficient to further develop the character of OSM as a digital commons. In this context, it also remains to be seen whether OSM will become more involved and cooperate with governmental actors. However, this must be the community's intention, as it could turn essential elements of the project structure upside down.

References

[1] Kilday, B. (2018). *Never lost again: The Google mapping revolution that sparked new industries and augmented our reality*. Harper Business, New York, NY.

- [2] Schröder-Bergen, S., Glasze, G., Michel, B., & Dammann, F. (2022). De/colonizing OpenStreetMap?. *GeoJournal*, 87(6), 5051–5066.
- [3] Schröder-Bergen, S. (2020). Analyzing the localness of OSM data. In M. Minghini, S. Coetzee, L. Juhász, A. Y. Grinberger, P. Mooney, & G. Yeboah (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Academic Track at the State of the Map 2020* (pp. 19-20). Zenodo.
- [4] Madubedube, A., Coetzee, S., & Rautenbach, V. (2021). A contributor-focused intrinsic quality assessment of OpenStreetMap in Mozambique using unsupervised machine learning. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 10(3), 156.
- [5] Mustard, A. (2020). *Winds of Change in OpenStreetMap*. State of the Map 2020. <https://2020.stateofthemap.org/sessions/RRVNAM/>
- [6] Steele, A. L. (2022). Mapping crises, communities and capitalism on OpenStreetMap: situating humanitarian mapping in the (open source) mapping supply chain. In M. Minghini, P. Liu, H. Li, A. Y. Grinberger, & L. Juhász (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022* (pp. 10–12). Zenodo.
- [7] Michel, B., & Schröder-Bergen, S. (2022). The Politics of Geodata in Urban Platform Capitalism. In A. Strüver, & S. Bauriedl (Eds.), *Platformization of Urban Life - Towards a Technocapitalist Transformation of European Cities* (pp. 73-84). transcript Verlag. <https://doi.org/10.14361/978383839459645-005>
- [8] Dulong de Rosnay, M., & Le Hervé Crosnier, H. (2012). An Introduction to the Digital Commons: From Common-Pool Resources to Community Governance. *Building Institutions for Sustainable Scientific, Cultural and Genetic Resources Commons* (pp. 1–18). <https://shs.hal.science/halshs-00736920>
- [9] Linebaugh, P. (2007). *The Magna Carta Manifesto: Liberties and Commons for All*. University of California Press.